

REFLECTIVE JOURNAL WRITING AND LEARNER AUTONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The current study was an endeavor to investigate the impact of practicing reflective journal writing on learner autonomy and its dimensions as well as language proficiency. It also aimed at finding the students attitude toward practicing the technique. The study enjoyed a quasi-experimental pretest post test design. To meet the objectives, 48 intermediate participants were assigned to a control (25 participants) and an experimental group (23 participants). Students' proficiencies were investigated in both pretest and post test using the same versions of PET. Students' level of autonomy was also studied in both pre-test and post-test utilizing a multidimensional learner autonomy questionnaire. Reflective journal writing was practiced over a three-month period in 23 sessions. T-test analysis of the results of the post test proficiency test revealed the positive impact of the technique on language proficiency. Although the t-tests run to analyze the different dimensions of the questionnaire showed the improvement in just three dimensions of learner autonomy, an improvement in learner autonomy in general was indicated. To study the participants' attitudes toward journal writing, the researcher asked the participants to write about their experience of writing reflective journals. The content analysis of the participants written experts indicated their positive attitudes toward using the technique.

Key words: Reflective journal writing, learner autonomy, language proficiency, attitudes

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of learner autonomy has been the focus of liberalists humanist thought since the 18th century (1). However, the concept came to the forefront as an educational goal in the twentieth century in social sciences, psychology, philosophy, and political science(2). The concept of autonomy in language learning started to take root in early 1970s but there was no attempt to integrate self-access language learning into the school curriculum until the late 1980s(3-6).

The last 25 years, second language acquisition research literature has witnessed an increasing attention to learner autonomy by focusing on learner reflection and taking responsibility for one's own learning processes, self-directed learning, self-access systems and individualized/independent learning. Interest in the idea of autonomy has grown largely since then and it has been associated with various forms of practice including individualized learning, self-instruction, self-access, computer-assisted language learning, distance learning, learner training and strategy training, collaborative learning, project work and the process or negotiated syllabus i.e. practices viewed as productive in fostering language learner autonomy and closely in contrast to the orthodoxy of the traditional language classroom in the 1970s and 1980s(7). More recently, however, autonomy has been presented as a more general goal which can be practiced in conventional classroom situations(8).

Raising awareness of process of learning in the language learners sounds an integral part of achieving autonomy. The effectiveness of encouraging students' self-assessment and monitoring through guided journal writing can be useful in fostering learner autonomy. Writing reflective journals can help the learner to see back for what he has done in the process of learning and consequently find the opportunity to become autonomous learner(9).

Reflective journals have been recommended as a key tool for developing reflective skills(10). Reflective writing is a process where one can learn from his experiences and is often used to 'reflect

forward' to the future as well as 'reflect back' on the past(11). Learning journals are believed to help learners to be autonomous, develop learners' writing skills, express their feelings, and provide an opportunity to think both about what they are learning and how they are learning and can enhance memory of the things learners have learned(12). Learner's journal is "some form of personal reflective writing" that helps students understand themselves and make sense of their experiences"(13). Several experiential learning techniques which include personal journals and reflection have been suggested to learner autonomy (14).

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study was an endeavor to investigate the impact of reflective journal writing on learner autonomy, so the following research question was put forth:

- Does practicing reflective journal writing foster learner autonomy?
- Does practicing reflective journal writing improve language proficiency?
- What are the learners' attitudes toward reflective journal writing?

3. METHODOLOGY

To answer the research question, a quasi- experimental design including a pretest and a posttest was used. The participants were 48 adult English learners, both male and female, all intermediate based on the results of PET as the proficiency test. None of the candidates knew that they were part of a research project to ensure the validity of the results. The study started in the fall, 2012 and took 3 months or one semester.

Preliminary English Test (PET) was administered to 59 English learners to ensure the homogeneity of the groups. Based on the results, twenty five students were selected out of the thirty to serve as the participants in the control group. Twenty three out of twenty nine students in the second class were chosen to serve as the experimental group.

A learner autonomy questionnaire was used as both a pretest and post test to measure the students' autonomy. To observe the extent to which learners are autonomous a Learner Autonomy Questionnaire was administered with reported the reliability of about.80 (based on Cronbach Alpha) was used. The questionnaire includes 44 statements based on nine dimensions related to autonomy in language learning. The questionnaire is based on the one used in Turkish context (15); however, it was modified and tailored to the Iranian context, after piloting the test to 20 students, and based on the experts ideas. Some questionnaires administered in Iranian EFL context was also examined to find items suitable for replacing the inappropriate items(16-19). The Learner Autonomy Questionnaire was administered to the student was given to the learners in the beginning of the semester (as the pre-test of autonomy).

Participants in the experimental group were asked to write reflective journals during the semester. The students were supposed to write a passage about what they learned, how they felt about the learning experience, how they evaluated themselves or their classmates and write down any other thoughts they may like to put on the paper. To ensure that the students know what to do exactly, they were given some journal samples.

At the end of the course, the same autonomy questionnaires were given to the students to determine the possible changes. The students were also given an open-ended questionnaire about their experience of learning writing journals. The same version of PET test was used to find any significant difference between the classes which have practiced different dimensions to autonomy and the conventional ones.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

To answer the first research question, the results on the autonomy questionnaire used in the study as the pre test and post test were analyzed using descriptive data analysis and t-test to see the differences between the experimental groups and the control group.

Table 1. LAQ pre-test

	VAR02	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
VAR01	Control	25	111.60	11.95	.96	47	.549
	RJW	23	113.34	10.11			

As shown in the table above, the learners in the groups were not significantly different in the Alpha decision level of .05, since the significance level observed is .549

Table 2. LAQ post-test

	VAR02	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
VAR01	Control	25	118.88	12.18	3.11	47	.003
	RJW	23	129.21	10.66			

As indicated above, there has been a significant difference between the groups and the practice of RJW has had a significant impact on learner autonomy as a whole. The sig. of .003 which is lower than the alpha decision level (.05) clearly shows this difference.

To shed light on the impact of journal writing on different dimensions of learner autonomy, different dimensions of LAQ were analyzed separately using t-test.

Table 3. The statistics for the impact of RJW on different dimensions of learner autonomy

Dimensions	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
D1	Control	25	20.16	2.37	2.05	46	.046
	RJW	23	21.52	2.21			
D2	Control	25	18.32	1.81	1.79	46	.540
	RJW	23	19.34	2.12			
D3	Control	25	21.24	2.58	2.23	46	.70
	RJW	23	23.04	2.96			
D4	Control	25	14.40	1.75	1.68	46	.072
	RJW	23	15.26	1.90			
D5	Control	25	09.08	2.08	.457	46	.650
	RJW	23	09.34	1.96			
D6	Control	25	07.40	1.52	1.08	46	.280
	RJW	23	07.95	1.98			
D7	Control	25	05.40	1.82	4.52	46	.000
	RJW	23	07.43	1.19			
D8	control	25	13.68	2.10	2.80	46	.007
	RJW	23	15.30	1.89			
D9	control	25	09.20	2.06	1.31	46	.193
	RJW	23	10.04	2.36			

As shown in table 4. in dimensions 1, 7 and 8 the sig (two-tailed) levels are .046, .00 and .007 respectively which are smaller than alpha decision level ($\alpha < .05$) set for this study. Therefore, it can be concluded that RJW has a significant impact on dimension 1, 7, and 8 of learner autonomy that is dimension of readiness for *self direction, intrinsic motivation and self assessment*. The mean of post-test PETs were compared using t-test to determine any significant difference between the groups.

Table 4. Statistics for PET as the post test

	VAR02	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
VAR01	Control	25	65.64	5.40	2.42	46	.019
	RJW	23	69.47	5.54			

As shown in the table the significance level is smaller than the alpha decision level and thereby the null hypothesis can be rejected and it can be claimed that reflective journal writing can improve learners' language proficiency.

To answer the third research questions students in the experimental group were asked to write about their experience of writing reflective journals. They were directed to respond to a set of specific questions in their writings. They were supposed to answer whether they enjoyed the experience, used it in their learning, found it useful in remembering the material in class better and helpful in understanding their previous lessons. Most of the learners demonstrated a positive attitude toward the usefulness of the technique. Below are some examples extracted from the students' writings:

Student 1: I think journal writing is very good because I have to open my book again and learn the lesson at home. In my opinion, when I write something I learn it better and remember it for a longer time. it's better than doing the workbook.

Student 2: In my opinion, writing journals was interesting for me because I enjoyed reading it in the classroom and expressing my ideas of my teacher and classroom. It is interesting also because you have to review all you have learned in the classroom at home. After writing the journal you know that you have learned a lot.

Student 3: When I was writing my journal, I had to work on my book more than ever. sometimes I needed some word, so I checked my dictionary to find the words and I learned a lot of words and phrases..... before the exam I read my journal to remember everything.

Student 4: I think the best part of journal writing was reading it in the class. It was funny to speak about the teacher's mood in the previous session.....and it encouraged me to use what I learned in the classroom in my conversations.

Most of the learners have the same positive responses on the use of reflective journal writing. Two of the learners, however, developed a negative attitude toward reflective journal writing and regarded it as a boring process with recurring themes.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Autonomy has been defined as a *capacity* – for detachment, critical reflection, decision-making and independent action (20). The principle of reflectivity which necessitates that learners engage in reflection in order to monitor and plan their learning in learner autonomy has been emphasized. To engage the learners in reflection, reflective journal writing can be fruitful and as the findings of the current study suggest practicing the technique has positive impacts on learner autonomy (21).

Although reflective journal writing had positive impact on learner autonomy in general, the dimensional study of the questionnaire results showed improvement in just some of the dimensions of learner autonomy as readiness for self direction, objective/evaluation and assessment/motivation. The last two dimensions developed are closely related to the practice of reflective journal writing which is in itself a kind of self-assessment or evaluation technique. The development of readiness for self direction may; however, be a surprise. Reflective journal writing fosters learner autonomy in general; the result which is in accordance with a study which has come to the same conclusion in Vietnam (22). The findings can also confirm the results found in a study which explored closely how students' use of blogs supports autonomous learning as the result of reflective and social processes (23). The findings also go with findings on how to develop autonomy using group work and reflective journal writing (24-25)

Reflective journal writing also positively affected language proficiency. Although there is no same study but this coincides with study on the effects of dialogue journals on L2 students' writing fluency (26).

The findings of the current study suggest several pedagogical implications for second or foreign language teaching and learning experts as well as textbook writers and curriculum designers. First of all teacher should care about learner autonomy since there are not going to support their students lifetime. It's the students right to take control of their own learning. They should also note that autonomy doesn't get to the end in a day or weeks, so patience should be exercised. From aforementioned findings, it is suggested that the EFL teachers should create opportunities for their students to express ideas about what they have learned and what they are not able to acquire or follow after every class. From this, teachers can adjust their teaching methods to meet the students' needs. In addition, not only teachers but also administrators need to recognize that improving learning autonomy for students is as important as increasing training quality for the institute. As a result, it is necessary to encourage learners in general and EFL learners in particular, that self-reflection, self-learning and self-researching are especially important in changing traditional learning habits. Reflective journal writing can also raise the students' awareness of their own learning and their strengths and weaknesses.

Developing learner autonomy, however, is not a matter of practicing one or two techniques; rather it needs a planned approach. Using the technique discussed, although, may lead to fostering autonomy but can not develop all its dimensions. It's the multidimensional model that can develop the autonomy and all its aspects. The multidimensional model can also affect the learner's proficiency which seems to be the end goal to many language teachers.

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